

Smart Surveillance and Gender-based Violence

Smart technologies (e.g., smartphones, smart home devices, wearables, AI-based applications) **not only enable and intensify existing forms of violence, but also introduce new modes of abuse, expand the methods available to perpetrators, and make violence increasingly subtle and harder to detect.** The risks are diverse and primarily concern surveillance, control, manipulation, and abuse.

Gender-based Violence is a Widespread, Everyday Problem

- Gender-based violence (GBV) disproportionately affects women, LGBTQI+ people (lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, intersex), and others who do not conform to heterosexual norms or traditional binary gender categories.
- Perpetrators are most often men, typically known to the victim/survivor – such as ex/partners, family members, or friends.
- Examples of GBV include:
 - Domestic violence
 - Femicide (the gender-related killing of women)
 - Forced marriage
 - Bullying and stalking
 - Threats, insults, and coercive control.
- Most GBV occurs in private spaces, particularly in the home, but also in public space and online.

What Are the New Risks Introduced by Smart Technologies?

Smart Technologies Risks

Tracking via wearables

Smart home control

Stalkerware & spyware

Control over online accounts

Identity theft

Tracking via wearables

GPS-enabled fitness trackers or smartwatches can be used to track someone's movements without their knowledge. This facilitates surveillance, stalking, post-separation abuse, and even control of routines and behaviours.

Smart home control

Smart locks, thermostats, cameras, or voice assistants (e.g. Alexa, Siri) can be misused to intimidate, isolate, or control. Examples include repeatedly turning lights or heating on/off, locking someone in or out of the home, or cutting off internet access, thereby exerting psychological pressure or isolating the victim.

Stalkerware & spyware

Perpetrators secretly install tracking software on the mobile devices of current or former partners to monitor their location, communications, and activities.

Control over online accounts

Perpetrators may gain or retain access to social media, email, or banking accounts, to manipulate, isolate, or financially abuse victims – for example by changing passwords or draining funds.

Identity theft

Perpetrator posing as the victim/survivor negatively affecting work, obtaining credit under the victim's/survivor's name, blocking / erasing / editing social media accounts.

What Can Be Done About It?

Policy

Legislation must require that manufacturers of tracking devices and smart technologies implement safety and anti-abuse features by design and by default.

Law Enforcement

Legal systems and police authorities must be properly trained and technically equipped to detect, understand, and respond to technology-facilitated abuse.

Prevention and Platform Responsibility

Technology companies, online platforms, and device manufacturers must develop and implement effective protective mechanisms, e.g. tracking devices should be designed with built-in safety features, such as notifications when an unknown tracker is detected nearby, or automatic deactivation when a tracker is separated from its registered 'home base' for an extended period.

Domestic Violence Shelters

Shelters must be equipped with devices that can detect hidden trackers, such as Bluetooth scanners or anti-surveillance tools, to ensure the safety of residents.

Public Education

The public must be informed about the threats posed by digital surveillance and control. Individuals should be equipped with digital literacy, knowledge of privacy settings, and practical strategies to prevent or respond to technology-enabled abuse.

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